

Supplementary Material

Title:

Polar lipid profile of *Saccharina latissima*, a functional food from the sea

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Supplementary Figure S1 Monogalactosyl diacylglycerol (MGDG) identification. a) HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of MGDG (32:2; 18:2/14:0) corresponding to $[M+\text{NH}_4]^+$ ion at m/z 744.6. b) Confirmation of galactolipid class was achieved by the identification of the combined neutral loss of hexose moiety (-180 Da) and NH_3 (-17 Da), corresponding to the loss of the head group of MGDG. Molecular species composition was confirmed by the identification of product ions corresponding to fatty acyl groups as acylium ions plus 74 ($\text{R}=\text{C}=\text{O} + 74$) seen at m/z 285.2 and m/z 337.3 [1,2].

Supplementary Figure S2 Digalactosyl diacylglycerol (DGDG) identification. a) HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of DGDG (38:9; 20:5/18:4) corresponding to $[M+\text{NH}_4]^+$ ion at m/z 976.6. b) Confirmation of galactolipid class was achieved by the identification of the neutral loss of two hexoses (loss of 180 Da + 162 Da) combined with loss of NH_3 (-17 Da) (total loss of 359 Da), corresponding to the loss of the head group of DGDG. Molecular species composition was confirmed by the identification of product ions corresponding to fatty acyl groups as acylium ions plus 74 ($R=C=O + 74$) seen at m/z 333.2 and m/z 359.3 [1,2].

Supplementary Figure S3 Sulfoquinovosyl diacylglycerol (SQDG) identification. a) HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of SQDG (34:3; 18:3/16:0) corresponding to $[M-H]^-$ ion at m/z 815.5. b) Confirmation of sulfolipid class was achieved by the identification of the ion at m/z 225 correspondent to the sulfoquinovosyl group of the polar head of SQDG. Molecular species composition was confirmed by the identification of product ions corresponding to the neutral loss of fatty acyl chains ($-RCOOH$) seen at m/z 537.3 and m/z 559.3 and by carboxylate anions $[RCOO]^-$ seen at m/z 255.2 and m/z 277.2 [2,3].

Supplementary Figure S4 Phosphatidylglycerol (PG) identification. HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of PG (34:1; 16:0 /18:1) corresponding to $[M-H]^-$ ion at m/z 747.5. Confirmation of phospholipid class was achieved by the identification of the ions at m/z 153, m/z 171 and m/z 227, corresponding to glycerol phosphate anion – H₂O, glycerol phosphate anion and glycerolphosphate glycerol anion –H₂O, respectively. Molecular species composition was confirmed by the identification of product ions corresponding to the fatty acyl chains as carboxylate anions $[RCOO]^-$ seen at m/z 255.2 and m/z 281.2 [1].

Supplementary Figure S5 Phosphatidylcholine (PC) identification. a) HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of PC (34:4; 14:0/20:4) corresponding to $[M+H]^+$ ion at m/z 754.5 in positive mode. b) Confirmation of phospholipid class was achieved by the identification of the ion at m/z 184 corresponding to the phosphocoline cation, typical product ion of the polar head, in the positive mode. c) HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of PC (34:4) as $[M+CH_3COO]^-$ ion at m/z 812.5 in negative mode. d) Molecular species composition was confirmed by the identification of product ions corresponding to the fatty acyl chains as carboxylate anions $[RCOO]^-$ seen at m/z 227.2 and m/z 303.2 [1].

Supplementary Figure S6 Phosphatidylethanolamine (PE) identification a) HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum of phosphatidylethanolamine (PE) molecular species detected as $[M+H]^+$ ions in *Saccharina latissima* samples. b) Molecular species of PE identified in the samples (C represents the total number of carbon atoms and N the total number of double bonds on the fatty acyl chains; bold m/z values correspond to the most abundant molecular species detected in HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum). Molecular species identified only by mass accuracy. c) HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of PE (30:3) corresponds to $[M+H]^+$ ion at m/z 658.4. d) Confirmation of phospholipid class was achieved by the identification of typical neutral loss of -141 Da corresponding to phosphoethanolamine from the polar head group of PE, in positive mode [1].

b)

$[M-H]^-$ m/z	Lipid species (C:N)	Fatty acyl chain
571.2893	LPI(16:0)	16:0
597.3047	LPI(18:1)	18:1
599.3212	LPI(18:0)	18:0
655.3831	LPI(22:0)	22:0

Supplementary Figure S7 Lysophosphatidylinositol (LPI) identification a) HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum of lysophosphatidylinositol (LPI) molecular species detected as $[M-H]^-$ ions in *Saccharina latissima* samples. b) Molecular species of LPI identified in the samples (C represents the total number of carbon atoms and N the total number of double bonds on the fatty acyl chains). Molecular species identified by mass accuracy.

Supplementary Figure S8 Phosphatidylinositol (PI) Identification a) HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum of phosphatidylinositol (PI) molecular species detected as $[M-H]^-$ ions in *Saccharina latissima* samples. b) Molecular species of PI identified in the samples (C represents the total number of carbon atoms and N the total number of double bonds on the fatty acyl chains; bold m/z value corresponds to the most abundant molecular species detected in HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum). c) HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of PI (34:1; 16:0/18:1) corresponding to $[M-H]^-$ ion at m/z 835.5. d) Confirmation of phospholipid class was achieved by the identification of the product ions at m/z 223, m/z 241, m/z 297 and m/z 315, reflecting the inositol head group. Molecular species composition was confirmed by the identification of product ions corresponding to the fatty acyl chains as carboxylate anions $[RCOO]^-$ seen at m/z 255.2 and m/z 281.2 [1].

Supplementary Figure S9 Phosphatidic acid (PA) identification a) HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum of phosphatidic acid (PA) molecular species detected as $[M-H]^-$ ions in *Saccharina latissima* samples. b) Molecular species of PA identified in the samples (C represents the total number of carbon atoms and N the total number of double bonds on the fatty acyl chains; bold m/z value corresponds to the most abundant molecular species detected in HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum). **Molecular species identified only by mass accuracy. c) HILIC-ESI/MS spectrum of PA (30:0; 14:0/16:0), corresponding to $[M-H]^-$ ion at m/z 619.4 in negative mode. d) Confirmation of phospholipid class was achieved by the identification of the ions at m/z 153, corresponding to glycerol phosphate anion $-H_2O$. Molecular species composition was confirmed by the identification of product ions corresponding to the fatty acyl chains as carboxylate anions $[RCOO]^-$ seen at m/z 227.2 and m/z 255.2 or by the neutral loss of ($-RCOOH$) [1].

Supplementary Figure S10 Arsenic-containing phospholipids (AsPL) a) HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum of arsenic-containing phospholipids (AsPL) molecular species detected as $[M+H]^+$ ions in *Saccharina latissima* samples. b) Molecular species of AsPL identified in the samples (C represents the total number of carbon atoms and N the total number of double bonds on the fatty acyl chains; bold m/z value corresponds to the most abundant molecular species detected in HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum). * Molecular species identified by interpretation of HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum c) HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of AsPL (32:0) corresponding to $[M+H]^+$ ion at m/z 959.5. d) Confirmation of lipid class was achieved by the identification of the product

ions at m/z 237, m/z 329, m/z 391, m/z 409, corresponding to the fragmentation of As- Sugar- PO_4 moiety [4].

Supplementary Figure S11 Diacylglyceryl-N,N,N-trimethyl homoserine (DGTS) identification a) HILIC-ESI-MS spectrum of diacylglyceryl-N,N,N-trimethyl homoserine (DGTS) molecular species detected as $[M+H]^+$ ions in *Saccharina latissima* samples. b) Molecular species of betaine lipids (monoacylglyceryl-N,N,N-trimethyl homoserine, MGTS and DGTS) identified in the samples (C represents the total number of carbon atoms and N the total number of double bonds on the fatty acyl chains). ** Molecular species identified only by mass accuracy. c) HILIC-ESI-MS/MS spectrum of DGTS (34:2; 16:1/18:1) corresponding to $[M+H]^+$ ion at m/z 736.6. d) Confirmation of lipid class was achieved by the identification of the product ion at m/z 236, corresponding to $C_{10}H_{22}O_5N^+$ from the polar head group. Molecular species composition was confirmed by the identification of neutral losses of fatty acyl chains as (-RCOOH) seen at m/z 454.3 and 482.4 and/or ketene ($R=C=O$) seen at m/z 472.4 and m/z 500.4 [2,3].

Supplementary Figure S12 Total ion chromatogram (TIC) LC-MS of total lipid extract and reconstructed ion chromatogram (RIC) of *Saccharina latissima* samples in a) positive mode and b) negative mode.

Abbreviations:

AsPL– Arsenic-containing phospholipids

DGDG – Digalactosyl diacylglycerol
DGTS – Diacylglyceryl-N,N,N-trimethyl homoserine
MGDG – Monogalactosyl diacylglycerol
LPC – Lysophosphatidylcholine
PA – Phosphatidic acid
PC – Phosphatidylcholine
PE – Phosphatidylethanolamine
PG – Phosphatidylglycerol
PI – Phosphatidylinositol
SQDG – Sulfoquinovosyl diacylglycerol
SQMG – Sulfoquinovosyl monoacylglycerol

Supplementary Table S1 Total molecular species identified by mass accuracy HILIC-LC-MS analysis in *Saccharina latissima* samples. C represents the total number of carbon atoms and N the total number of double bonds on the fatty acyl chains.

Monogalactosyl diacylglycerol (MGDG)

[M+NH₄]⁺	[M+NH₄]⁺			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
740.5305	740.5307	MGDG(32:4)	C41H74NO10	-0.270
742.5461	742.5464	MGDG(32:3)	C41H76NO10	-0.404
744.5610	744.5620	MGDG(32:2)	C41H78NO10	-1.343
746.5780	746.5777	MGDG(32:1)	C41H80NO10	0.402
748.5941	748.5939	MGDG(32:0)	C41H82NO10	0.302
768.5624	768.5620	MGDG(34:4)	C43H78NO10	0.520
770.5755	770.5782	MGDG(34:3)	C43H80NO10	-3.535
772.5932	772.5933	MGDG(34:2)	C43H82NO10	-0.129
774.6090	774.6090	MGDG(34:1)	C43H84NO10	0.000
776.6229	776.6246	MGDG(34:0)	C43H86NO10	-2.189
788.5296	788.5313	MGDG(36:8)	C45H74NO10	-2.118
790.5458	790.5469	MGDG(36:7)	C45H76NO10	-1.391
814.5462	814.5469	MGDG(38:9)	C47H76NO10	-0.889
828.6591	828.6565	MGDG(38:2)	C47H90NO10	3.174

Digalactosyl diacylglycerol (DGDG)

[M+NH₄]⁺	[M+NH₄]⁺			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
902.5854	902.5841	DGDG(32:4)	C47H84O15N	1.440
904.5981	904.5997	DGDG(32:3)	C47H86O15N	-1.769
906.6140	906.6154	DGDG(32:2)	C47H88O15N	-1.544
908.6299	908.6310	DGDG(32:1)	C47H90O15N	-1.211
932.6304	932.6310	DGDG(34:3)	C49H90O15N	-0.643
934.6461	934.6467	DGDG(34:2)	C49H92O15N	-0.642
936.6613	936.6623	DGDG(34:1)	C49H94O15N	-1.068
938.6765	938.6780	DGDG(34:0)	C49H96O15N	-1.598
950.5841	950.5841	DGDG(36:8)	C51H84O15N	0.000
952.5982	952.5997	DGDG(36:7)	C51H86O15N	-1.575
956.6315	956.6310	DGDG(36:5)	C51H90O15N	0.523
976.5979	976.5997	DGDG(38:9)	C53H86O15N	-1.843
978.6127	978.6154	DGDG(38:8)	C53H88O15N	-2.759
980.6276	980.6310	DGDG(38:7)	C53H90O15N	-3.467
984.6610	984.6623	DGDG(38:5)	C53H94O15N	-1.320

Sulfoquinovosyl monoacylglycerol (SQMG)

[M-H]⁻	[M-H]⁻			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
555.2838	555.2839	SQMG(16:0)	C25H47O11S	-0.202
575.2532	575.2526	SQMG(18:4)	C27H43O11S	1.022
581.3002	581.2996	SQMG(18:1)	C27H49O11S	1.099

Sulfoquinovosyl diacylglycerol (SQDG)

[M-H]⁻	[M-H]⁻			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
737.4512	737.4510	SQDG(28:0)	C37H69O12S	0.302
763.4662	763.4666	SQDG(30:1)	C39H71O12S	-0.559
765.4815	765.4823	SQDG(30:0)	C39H73O12S	-1.015
779.4947	779.4985	SQDG(31:0)	C40H75O12S	-4.875
785.4514	785.4510	SQDG(32:4)	C41H69O12S	0.539
787.4663	787.4666	SQDG(32:3)	C41H71O12S	-0.415
791.4974	791.4979	SQDG(32:1)	C41H75O12S	-0.666
793.5121	793.5136	SQDG(32:0)	C41H77O12S	-1.860
805.5127	805.5141	SQDG(33:1)	C42H77O12S	-1.738
807.5264	807.5298	SQDG(33:0)	C42H79O12S	-4.210
813.4834	813.4823	SQDG(34:4)	C43H73O12S	1.380
815.4967	815.4979	SQDG(34:3)	C43H75O12S	-1.505
817.5134	817.5136	SQDG(34:2)	C43H77O12S	-0.215
819.5299	819.5292	SQDG(34:1)	C43H79O12S	0.821
821.5437	821.5449	SQDG(34:0)	C43H81O12S	-1.433
833.5430	833.5454	SQDG(35:1)	C44H81O12S	-2.879
835.5604	835.5611	SQDG(35:0)	C44H83O12S	-0.838
837.4837	837.4823	SQDG(36:6)	C45H73O12S	1.699
839.4970	839.4979	SQDG(36:5)	C45H75O12S	-1.104
841.5135	841.5136	SQDG(36:4)	C45H77O12S	-0.090
843.5277	843.5292	SQDG(36:3)	C45H79O12S	-1.810
845.5448	845.5449	SQDG(36:2)	C45H81O12S	-0.091
849.5760	849.5762	SQDG(36:0)	C45H85O12S	-0.208
859.4665	859.4666	SQDG(38:9)	C47H71O12S	-0.148
871.5601	871.5605	SQDG(38:3)	C47H83O12S	-0.490

Lysophosphatidylglycerol (LPG)

[M-H]⁻	[M-H]⁻			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
481.2570	481.2566	LPG(16:1)	C22H42O9P	0.731
483.2730	483.2723	LPG(16:0)	C22H44O9P	1.453
505.2569	505.2566	LPG(18:3)	C24H42O9P	0.499
507.2732	507.2723	LPG(18:2)	C24H44O9P	1.778
509.2880	509.2879	LPG(18:1)	C24H46O9P	0.102
529.2578	529.2566	LPG(20:5)	C26H42O9P	2.177
535.3038	535.3036	LPG(20:2)	C26H48O9P	0.377
557.2894	557.2879	LPG(22:5)	C28H46O9P	2.605

Phosphatidylglycerol (PG)

[M-H]⁻	[M-H]⁻			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
691.4550	691.4550	PG(30:1)	C36H68O10P	0.000
693.4710	693.4707	PG(30:0)	C36H70O10P	0.433
717.4714	717.4707	PG(32:2)	C38H70O10P	0.976
719.4861	719.4863	PG(32:1)	C38H72O10P	-0.278
721.5025	721.5020	PG(32:0)	C38H74O10P	0.693
739.4547	739.4550	PG(34:5)	C40H68O10P	-0.406
741.4700	741.4707	PG(34:4)	C40H70O10P	-0.944
743.4863	743.4863	PG(34:3)	C40H72O10P	0.000
745.5026	745.5020	PG(34:2)	C40H74O10P	0.805
747.5187	747.5176	PG(34:1)	C40H76O10P	1.472
749.5336	749.5333	PG(34:0)	C40H78O10P	0.400
759.5147	759.5182	PG(35:2)	C41H76O10P	-4.608
761.5335	761.5338	PG(35:1)	C41H78O10P	-0.394
763.5499	763.5495	PG(35:0)	C41H80O10P	0.524
765.4717	765.4707	PG(36:6)	C42H70O10P	1.306
767.4866	767.4863	PG(36:5)	C42H72O10P	0.391
769.5027	769.5020	PG(36:4)	C42H74O10P	0.910
771.5176	771.5176	PG(36:3)	C42H76O10P	0.000
773.5332	773.5333	PG(36:2)	C42H78O10P	-0.129
775.5475	775.5489	PG(36:1)	C42H80O10P	-1.805
795.5174	795.5176	PG(38:5)	C44H76O10P	-0.251
821.5329	821.5333	PG(40:6)	C46H78O10P	-0.487

Lysohosphatidylcholine (LPC)

[M+H]⁺	[M+H]⁺			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
496.3392	496.3403	LPC(16:0)	C24H51NO7P	-2.248
518.3222	518.3247	LPC(18:3)	C26H49NO7P	-4.760
522.3566	522.3560	LPC(18:1)	C26H53NO7P	1.212
542.3229	542.3247	LPC(20:5)	C28H49NO7P	-3.258
544.3402	544.3403	LPC(20:4)	C28H51NO7P	-0.213
568.3387	568.3403	LPC(22:6)	C30H51NO7P	-2.843

Phosphatidylcholine (PC)

[M+H]⁺	[M+H]⁺			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
704.5249	704.5230	PC(30:1)	C38H75NO8P	2.651
726.5065	726.5074	PC(32:4)	C40H73NO8P	-1.214
728.5233	728.5230	PC(32:3)	C40H75NO8P	0.368
730.5370	730.5387	PC(32:2)	C40H77NO8P	-2.302
732.5538	732.5543	PC(32:1)	C40H79NO8P	-0.725
746.5667	746.5694	PC(33:1)	C41H81NO8P	-3.617
752.5230	752.5230	PC(34:5)	C42H75NO8P	-0.043
754.5388	754.5387	PC(34:4)	C42H77NO8P	0.156
756.5537	756.5543	PC(34:3)	C42H79NO8P	-0.834
758.5707	758.5700	PC(34:2)	C42H81NO8P	0.947
760.5838	760.5856	PC(34:1)	C42H83NO8P	-2.409
768.5533	768.5538	PC(35:4)	C43H79NO8P	-0.651
774.5065	774.5068	PC(36:8)	C44H73NO8P	-0.387
776.5200	776.5230	PC(36:7)	C44H75NO8P	-3.905
778.5359	778.5387	PC(36:6)	C44H77NO8P	-3.573
780.5525	780.5543	PC(36:5)	C44H79NO8P	-2.346
782.5679	782.5700	PC(36:4)	C44H81NO8P	-2.660
784.5849	784.5856	PC(36:3)	C44H83NO8P	-0.933
786.6004	786.6013	PC(36:2)	C44H85NO8P	-1.121
802.5370	802.5387	PC(38:8)	C46H77NO8P	-2.096
804.5516	804.5543	PC(38:7)	C46H79NO8P	-3.394
806.5685	806.5700	PC(38:6)	C46H81NO8P	-1.837
808.5829	808.5856	PC(38:5)	C46H83NO8P	-3.379
810.5993	810.6013	PC(38:4)	C46H85NO8P	-2.445
826.5384	826.5387	PC(40:10)	C48H77NO8P	-0.341
828.5539	828.5543	PC(40:9)	C48H79NO8P	-0.520

Phosphatidylcholine (PC) Cont.

[M+H]⁺	[M+H]⁺			
<i>m/z</i> Observed	<i>m/z</i> Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
830.5698	830.5700	PC(40:8)	C48H81NO8P	-0.219
832.5840	832.5856	PC(40:7)	C48H83NO8P	-1.960
834.5987	834.6013	PC(40:6)	C48H85NO8P	-3.094
852.5538	852.5543	PC(42:11)	C50H79NO8P	-0.623

Phosphatidylethanolamine (PE)

[M+H]⁺	[M+H]⁺			
<i>m/z</i> Observed	<i>m/z</i> Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
658.4425	658.4448	PE(30:3)	C35H65NO8P	-3.466
680.4286	680.4291	PE(32:6)	C37H63NO8P	-0.782
710.4768	710.4761	PE(34:5)	C39H69NO8P	1.011
716.5200	716.5230	PE(34:2)	C39H75NO8P	-4.232
738.5069	738.5074	PE(36:5)	C41H73O8NP	-0.653
740.5220	740.5230	PE(36:4)	C41H75NO8P	-1.394
746.5676	746.5700	PE(36:1)	C41H81O8NP	-3.191
762.5055	762.5074	PE(38:7)	C43H73NO8P	-2.468
774.6033	774.6013	PE(38:1)	C43H85O8NP	2.605
788.5235	788.5230	PE(40:8)	C45H75O8NP	0.594
790.5381	790.5387	PE(40:7)	C45H77NO8P	-0.736
792.5549	792.5543	PE(40:6)	C45H79O8NP	0.718

Lysophosphatidylinositol (LPI)

[M-H]⁻	[M-H]⁻			
<i>m/z</i> Observed	<i>m/z</i> Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
571.2893	571.2883	LPI(16:0)	C25H48O12P	1.677
597.3047	597.3040	LPI(18:1)	C27H50O12P	1.184
599.3212	599.3196	LPI(18:0)	C27H52O12P	2.598
655.3831	655.3822	LPI(22:0)	C31H60O12P	1.308

Phosphatidylinositol (PI)

[M-H]⁻	[M-H]⁻			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
779.4727	779.4711	PI(30:1)	C39H72O13P	2.053
781.4869	781.4867	PI(30:0)	C39H74O13P	0.256
803.4714	803.4711	PI(32:3)	C41H72O13P	0.373
805.4851	805.4867	PI(32:2)	C41H74O13P	-1.986
807.5036	807.5024	PI(32:1)	C41H76O13P	1.486
823.5338	823.5342	PI(33:0)	C42H80O13P	-0.486
829.4848	829.4867	PI(34:4)	C43H74O13P	-2.291
831.5028	831.5024	PI(34:3)	C43H76O13P	0.481
833.5190	833.5180	PI(34:2)	C43H78O13P	1.200
835.5323	835.5337	PI(34:1)	C43H80O13P	-1.676
837.5501	837.5493	PI(34:0)	C43H82O13P	0.955
847.5340	847.5342	PI(35:2)	C44H80O13P	-0.236
849.5485	849.5499	PI(35:1)	C44H82O13P	-1.648
855.5017	855.5024	PI(36:5)	C45H76O13P	-0.818
857.5168	857.5180	PI(36:4)	C45H78O13P	-1.399
859.5329	859.5337	PI(36:3)	C45H80O13P	-0.931
861.5493	861.5493	PI(36:2)	C45H82O13P	0.000
863.5644	863.5650	PI(36:1)	C45H84O13P	-0.695
877.4873	877.4867	PI(38:8)	C47H74O13P	0.684
883.5348	883.5337	PI(38:5)	C47H80O13P	1.245
885.5511	885.5493	PI(38:4)	C47H82O13P	2.033
909.5483	909.5493	PI(40:6)	C49H82O13P	-1.099

Phosphatidic acid (PA)

[M-H]⁻	[M-H]⁻			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
617.4199	617.4182	PA(30:1)	C33H62O8P	2.700
619.4345	619.4339	PA(30:0)	C33H64O8P	0.996
641.4172	641.4182	PA(32:3)	C35H62O8P	-1.610
643.4324	643.4339	PA(32:2)	C35H64O8P	-2.305
645.4491	645.4495	PA(32:1)	C35H66O8P	-0.600
667.4346	667.4339	PA(34:4)	C37H64O8P	1.074
669.4501	669.4495	PA(34:3)	C37H66O8P	0.847
673.4820	673.4808	PA(34:1)	C37H70O8P	1.733
695.4665	695.4652	PA(36:4)	C39H68O8P	1.894
723.4970	723.4965	PA(38:4)	C41H72O8P	0.715
741.4507	741.4495	PA(40:9)	C43H66O8P	1.574
743.4652	743.4652	PA(40:8)	C43H68O8P	0.023
745.4822	745.4808	PA(40:7)	C43H70O8P	1.834
765.4503	765.4495	PA(42:11)	C45H66O8P	1.002
773.5126	773.5121	PA(42:7)	C45H74O8P	0.604
795.4998	795.4965	PA(44:10)	C47H72O8P	4.170

Arsenic-containing phospholipids (AsPL)

[M + H]⁺	[M + H]⁺			
m/z Observed	m/z Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
931.4889	931.4893	AsPL(30:0)	C43H85AsO14P	-0.423
945.5045	945.5049	AsPL(31:0)	C44H87AsO14P	-0.470
953.4713	953.4736	AsPL(32:3)	C45H83AsO14P	-2.457
957.5021	957.5049	AsPL(32:1)	C45H87AsO14P	-2.970
959.5206	959.5206	AsPL(32:0)	C45H89AsO14P	0.006
973.5356	973.5362	AsPL(33:0)	C46H91AsO14P	-0.662
981.5031	981.5049	AsPL(34:3)	C47H87AsO14P	-1.879
985.5361	985.5362	AsPL(34:1)	C47H91AsO14P	-0.146
987.5522	987.5519	AsPL(34:0)	C47H93AsO14P	0.310
1001.5659	1001.5675	AsPL(35:0)	C48H95AsO14P	-1.641
1015.5842	1015.5832	AsPL(36:0)	C49H97AsO14P	0.991
1027.5850	1027.5832	AsPL(37:1)	C50H97AsO14P	1.758

Monoacylglyceryl-N,N,N-trimethyl homoserine (MGTS)**Diacylglyceryl-N,N,N-trimethyl homoserine (DGTS)**

[M + H]⁺	[M + H]⁺			
<i>m/z</i> Observed	<i>m/z</i> Library	Lipid species (C:N)	Formula	Delta ppm
470.3493	470.3482	MGTS(16:2)	C26H48O6N	2.415
682.5622	682.5622	DGTS(30:1)	C40H76O7N	0.000
708.5778	708.5778	DGTS(32:2)	C42H78O7N	0.000
710.5933	710.5935	DGTS(32:1)	C42H80O7N	-0.281
736.6086	736.6091	DGTS(34:2)	C44H82O7N	-0.679
746.5920	746.5935	DGTS(35:4)	C45H80O7N	-1.981
762.6245	762.6248	DGTS(36:3)	C46H84O7N	-0.393
764.6407	764.6404	DGTS(36:2)	C46H86O7N	0.392

Supplementary Table S2 Molecular species of lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC) identified in the *Saccharina latissima* samples as $[M+H]^+$ and $[M+CH_3COO]^-$ ions in positive and negative modes, respectively (C represents the total number of carbon atoms and N the total number of double bonds on the fatty acyl chains). Molecular species confirmed by interpretation of HILIC-ESI-MS/MS fragmentation and mass accuracy.

$[M+H]^+$ <i>m/z</i>	$[M+CH_3COO]^-$ <i>m/z</i>	Lipid species (C:N)	Fatty acyl chain
496.3392	554.3447	LPC(16:0)	16:0
518.3222	576.3302	LPC(18:3)	18:3
522.3566	580.3621	LPC(18:1)	18:1
542.3229	600.3284	LPC(20:5)	20:5
544.3402	602.3457	LPC(20:4)	20:4
568.3387	626.3442	LPC(22:6)	22:6

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